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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research****Article****ANALYSIS OF ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT BY PAR
INDEX IN PAKISTAN**¹Dr Zarish Anjum, ¹Dr Hurera Pervez, ¹Dr Ayesha Naveed¹Demontmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Introduction: Quantitative evaluation of Orthodontic diagnosis is considered to be a difficult task due to its subjective nature. On the contrary, several indices have been presented for quantitative assessment of severity of malocclusion and evaluation of treatment need. **Aims and objectives:** The main objective of the study is to analyze the orthodontic treatment by PAR index in Pakistan. **Material and methods:** This cross sectional study was conducted in Demontmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore during October 2018 to February 2019. The data was collected from 100 orthodontics patients of both genders. All the data was collected before and after treatment. The total PAR scores were measured. Information regarding patients' age, gender, angle's malocclusion, duration of active treatment, extraction or non-extraction was collected from their files. **Results:** The data was collected from 100 patients. The mean age was 35.67 ± 5.46 years. There was 100 % correction in upper and lower anterior segment followed by more than 85% correction in lower left, upper left, upper right, and right buccal segments respectively. Overbite was the only variable that ended up with less than 50 % correction. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that a significant positive correlation exists between pretreatment PAR score and point reduction.

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INTRODUCTION:

Quantitative evaluation of Orthodontic diagnosis is considered to be a difficult task due to its subjective nature. On the contrary, several indices have been presented for quantitative assessment of severity of malocclusion and evaluation of treatment need. These indices provide valid and reproducible system of measurement. The Peer Assessment Rating (PAR) index was introduced by Richmond in 1990 to assess the severity of malocclusion [1]. It provides a cumulative score for occlusal disharmonies and identifies a deviation between normal occlusion and malocclusion. It has been weighted according to the judgment of orthodontists and general dentists [2]. The malocclusion is quantified based on five criteria of variable weightings: upper and lower anterior segment alignment (x1), left and right buccal occlusion (x1), overjet (x6), overbite (x2), and centerline (x4). Pretreatment and post treatment study casts are used for and comparison. This comparison is used to judge treatment efficacy in correction of malocclusion. Reduction in the total score and percentage reduction are used to measure changes in PAR index [3].

It is unrealistic to expect all malocclusions to be treated to an ideal occlusion. The outcome of treatment is often dependent on many factors, e.g. complexity of the case and the expertise of the practitioner. It is, however, important to establish whether a worthwhile improvement has been achieved for an individual case and the proportion of cases that show improvement. The PAR index is primarily designed to look at the results of a group of patients, rather than an individual patient, as there are always a small number of patients where the index does not fully represent the result obtained [4]. The index is, however, generally accepted by the

British Orthodontic Society as a useful tool in this area. For its use to be accurate and reproducible, any individual providing a PAR scoring service must have first successfully passed an appropriate calibration test and have documentary evidence of this [5]. Unless an individual is calibrated on the use of the index, the results they produce will not be valid or reproducible and should not be used to assess the standard of someone else's treatment [6].

Aims and objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyze the orthodontic treatment by PAR index in Pakistan.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Demontmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore during October 2018 to February 2019. The data was collected from 100 orthodontics patients of both genders. All the data was collected before and after treatment. The total PAR scores were measured. Information regarding patients' age, gender, angle's malocclusion, duration of active treatment, extraction or non-extraction was collected from their files.

All the data was collected and analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. All the descriptive statistics were measured in mean and standard deviation values.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 100 patients. The mean age was 35.67 ± 5.46 years. There was 100 % correction in upper and lower anterior segment followed by more than 85% correction in lower left, upper left, upper right, and right buccal segments respectively. Overbite was the only variable that ended up with less than 50 % correction.

Table 01: PAR index analysis before and after treatment

	Class I		Class II		Class III	
	T1	T2	T1	T2	T1	T2
Mean	20.1	6	21.1	7	13	4
Max	34	15	36	19	12	4
Minimum	6	4	8	3	0	0

DISCUSSION:

We were able to highest percentage PAR reduction (78%) in Class II sub division malocclusion, followed closely by Class II division 1 and Class I malocclusion (77% and 76 % respectively) [6]. Lowest reduction was noted in Class III malocclusion (58%). These results are consistent with the results achieved by Gasgoos. However, the statistical relation between percentage reduction and malocclusions in both studies was insignificant. Treatment of Class II Division 1 group was found to

be most successful by Birkeland *et al* [7]. It was followed closely by Class II Division 2 malocclusion. In contrast to present study, their study design did not include class II sub division as a separate category. Fidler *et al* also found a high percentage reduction and better long term results in Class II malocclusion group [8].

A high standard of treatment may be judged according to the mean percentage reduction in weighted PAR score for an individual practitioner's

case load, for example, greater than 70 percent [9]. For a practitioner to produce high standards and treat those cases who have perhaps a greater need for treatment, the mean percentage reduction for the case load must not only be high (e.g. greater than 70 percent), but the percentage of cases having been 'greatly improved' should also be high [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that a significant positive correlation exists between pretreatment PAR score and point reduction.

REFERENCES:

1. Kaygisiz E, Uzuner FD, Taner L. A Comparison of Three Orthodontic Treatment Indices with Regard to Angle Classification. *Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*. 2016 Mar;40(2):169-74.
2. Richmond S. A critical evaluation of orthodontic treatment in the general dental services of England and Wales (Doctoral dissertation, University of Manchester).
3. Richmond S, Shaw WC, O'Brien KD, Buchanan IB, Jones R, Stephens CD, Roberts CT, Andrews M. The development of the PAR Index (Peer Assessment Rating): reliability and validity. *The European Journal of Orthodontics*. 1992 Apr;14(2):125-39.
4. Firestone AR, Häsler RU, Ingervall B. Treatment results in dental school orthodontic patients in 1983 and 1993. *The Angle Orthodontist*. 1999 Feb;69(1):19-26.
5. Green JI. An Overview of the Peer Assessment Rating (par) Index for Primary Dental Care Practitioners. *Primary dental journal*. 2016 Nov;5(4):28-37.
6. Pangrazio-Kulbersh V, Kaczynski R, Shunock M. Early treatment outcome assessed by the Peer Assessment Rating index. *American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics*. 1999 May ;115(5):544-50.
7. Liu S, Oh H, Chambers DW, Xu T, Baumrind S. Interpreting weightings of the peer assessment rating index and the discrepancy index across contexts on Chinese patients. *European journal of orthodontics*. 2017 Jun;40(2):157-63.
8. O'Brien KD, Shaw WC, Roberts CT. The use of occlusal indices in assessing the provision of orthodontic treatment by the hospital orthodontic service of England and Wales. *British Journal of Orthodontics*. 1993 Feb;20(1):25-35.
9. Freitas KM, Guirro WJ, de Freitas DS, de Freitas MR, Janson G. Relapse of anterior crowding 3 and 33 years postretention. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 2017 Dec;152(6):798-810.
10. Freitas KM, Janson G, Tompson B, de Freitas MR, Simão TM, Valarelli FP, Cançado RH. Posttreatment and physiologic occlusal changes comparison. *The Angle Orthodontist*. 2012 Jul ;83(2):239-45.